

Article

Indeterminacy Fuzzy Set coincides with the Picture Fuzzy Set, and both are particular cases of the Refined Neurosophic Set

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Abstract: In this short note, we analyze the relationship between C. Ardil’s Indeterminacy Fuzzy Set (IDFS) and Bui Cong Cuong’s Picture Fuzzy Set (PFS). We show that Ardil’s “epistemic freedom residual” mathematically coincides with Cuong’s “refusal degree,” and that the two formalisms satisfy the same admissible simplex constraint. Consequently, IDFS and PFS are mathematically equivalent representations under different notations and interpretations. Furthermore, we show that both structures can be regarded as particular cases of the n-refined neurosophic set and its generalized extensions.

Keywords: Indeterminacy Fuzzy Set, Picture Fuzzy Set, n-Refined Neurosophic Set, Nonstandard Refined Neurosophic Set, Refined Neurosophic Over/Under/Off-Set, Nonstandard Refined Neurosophic Over/Under/Off-Set.

1. Introduction

We present, for comparison, the definitions of Indeterminacy Fuzzy Set [1] and Picture Fuzzy Set [2] below, and it is clearly seeing that they are the same. Since the Picture Fuzzy Set was introduced in 2014 by Cuong [2], it may represent an earlier formulation of the same mathematical structure.

The other definitions below (n-Refined Neurosophic Set, Nonstandard Refined Neurosophic Set, Refined Neurosophic Over/Under/Off-Set, Nonstandard Refined Neurosophic Over/Under/Off-Set) are displayed because they are generalizations of the Indeterminacy Fuzzy Set (Picture Fuzzy Set).

2. Definition 1.

Indeterminacy Fuzzy Set. Let X be a nonempty universe. An IDFS A on X is

$$A = \{(x, TA(x), IA(x), FA(x)) \mid x \in X\},$$

where $TA, IA, FA : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ satisfy the simplex constraint $0 \leq TA(x) + IA(x) + FA(x) \leq 1$ ($\forall x \in X$).

(1) The quantity $qA(x) = 1 - TA(x) - IA(x) - FA(x) \geq 0$ is the epistemic freedom residual.

The admissible state space is the closed simplex

$$\Delta^* = \{(T, I, F) \in [0, 1]^3 \mid T + I + F \leq 1\}.$$

(2) The boundary $T + I + F = 1$ (i.e., $q = 0$) contains all IFS states embedded by

$$\Phi(\mu, \nu) = (\mu, 1 - \mu - \nu, \nu).$$

Interior points ($q > 0$) are exclusive to IDFS.

The maximum entropy IDFS state (1/4, 1/4, 1/4) with $\varrho = 1/4$ achieves entropy $\ln 4$, strictly exceeding the IFS maximum $\ln 3$. [1]

3. Definition 2.

Picture Fuzzy Set A on a universe X is an object in the form of

$$A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \eta_A(x), \nu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$$

where $\mu_A(x) \in [0, 1]$ is called the degree of positive membership of x in A , $\eta_A(x) \in [0, 1]$ is called the degree of neutral membership of x in A and $\nu_A(x) \in [0, 1]$ is called the degree of negative membership of x in A , and where μ_A , η_A and ν_A satisfy the following condition:

$$(\forall x \in X) (\mu_A(x) + \eta_A(x) + \nu_A(x) \leq 1).$$

Now $(1 - (\mu_A(x) + \eta_A(x) + \nu_A(x)))$ could be called the degree of refusal membership of x in A .

Let $PFS(X)$ denote the set of all the picture fuzzy sets on a universe X . Basically, picture fuzzy sets based models may be adequate in situations when we face human opinions involving more answers of types: yes, abstain, no, refusal. [2]

4. Theorem 1 (Equivalence of IDFS and PFS)

Let A be an Indeterminacy Fuzzy Set (IDFS) on universe X :

$$A = \{(x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$$

such that

$$T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 1.$$

Let B be a Picture Fuzzy Set (PFS):

$$B = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \eta_A(x), \nu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$$

with

$$\mu_A(x) + \eta_A(x) + \nu_A(x) \leq 1.$$

Then IDFS and PFS are mathematically equivalent under the bijective mapping:

$$\begin{aligned} T_A(x) &\leftrightarrow \mu_A(x), \\ I_A(x) &\leftrightarrow \eta_A(x), \\ F_A(x) &\leftrightarrow \nu_A(x). \end{aligned}$$

Moreover,

$$\rho_A(x) = 1 - T_A(x) - I_A(x) - F_A(x)$$

coincides with the Picture Fuzzy Set refusal degree:

$$\pi_A(x) = 1 - \mu_A(x) - \eta_A(x) - \nu_A(x).$$

Therefore,

$$\rho_A(x) = \pi_A(x),$$

which proves the equivalence of the two formalisms.

Proof.

Under the above correspondence between membership components, the admissible state spaces are identical since both satisfy the same simplex constraint. The residual quantity in IDFS equals the refusal degree in PFS through direct substitution. Hence every IDFS induces a unique PFS and vice versa, establishing a one-to-one correspondence. ■

5. Definition 3

Single-Valued n-Refined Neutrosophic Set/Logic/Probability [3], where there are many refinements $T_1, T_2, \dots, T_p; I_1, I_2, \dots, I_r; F_1, F_2, \dots, F_s$, with integers $p, r, s \geq 1$, and $p + r + s = n$, and all numerical $T_1, T_2, \dots, T_p, I_1, I_2, \dots, I_r, F_1, F_2, \dots, F_s \in [0, 1]$.

And Set-Valued n-Refined Neutrosophic Set/Logic/Probability, where similarly there are many refinements $T_1, T_2, \dots, T_p; I_1, I_2, \dots, I_r; F_1, F_2, \dots, F_s$, with integers $p, r, s \geq 1$ and $p + r + s = n$, and all subsets $T_1, T_2, \dots, T_p, I_1, I_2, \dots, I_r, F_1, F_2, \dots, F_s \subseteq [0, 1]$.

6. Definition 4

More generalization there is the Nonstandard Refined Neutrosophic Set [4] (within the Extended Nonstandard Analysis), where $T_1, T_2, \dots, T_p, I_1, I_2, \dots, I_r, F_1, F_2, \dots, F_s \in]0, 1+[$ and they may be reals, hyperreals, monads, or binads.

7. Definition 5

Further on, one has the **Refined Neutrosophic Over/Under/Off-Set/Logic/Probability** [3, 4], where all subcomponents $T_1, T_2, \dots, T_p, I_1, I_2, \dots, I_r, F_1, F_2, \dots, F_s \in [\Omega, \Psi]$, with $\Omega < 0 < 1 < \Psi$.

8. Definition 6

Also, **Nonstandard Refined Neutrosophic Over/Under/Off-Set/Logic/Probability**, where all subcomponents $T_1, T_2, \dots, T_p, I_1, I_2, \dots, I_r, F_1, F_2, \dots, F_s \in]-\Omega, \Psi+[$, with $\Omega < 0 < 1 < \Psi$, and they may be reals, hyperreals, monads, or binads (within Extended NonStandard Analysis). [4, 5]

9. Conclusion

Definitions 1 and 2 coincide, but using different notations. While the mathematical structure of the Indeterminacy Fuzzy Set coincides with that of the Picture Fuzzy Set, one may still distinguish the semantic interpretation of the residual component. In the IDFS framework, the quantity ρ is interpreted as an *epistemic freedom residual*, whereas in the PFS framework it is interpreted as a *refusal degree*. Therefore, the present note does not deny possible semantic reinterpretations, but rather establishes that the underlying mathematical formalism is equivalent.

References

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